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**SCREENING FOR TUMOR DISEASES OF THE REPRODUCTIVE
SYSTEM ORGANS: OPPORTUNITIES AND PROSPECTS****Abduxalilova Aziza Adxamovna****Azimova Guli Ravshanbek qizi****Safaraliyev Doniyor Diyorjon o'g'li**

Scientific supervisor: assistant of the Department of Pediatric Surgery No. 1

Abbasov Khozhimhammad Khabibulaevich

Samarkand State Medical University

Uzbekistan Samarkand

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The relevance of the problem of screening for tumor diseases of the reproductive organs (TDO) is due to high morbidity rates, a tendency towards "rejuvenation", and unsatisfactory results of therapy. In Russia, rates of active detection of acute respiratory disease, diagnosis in pre-invasive and early stages remain low, having an adverse impact on the quality and life expectancy of the patient and her reproductive function.

Purpose of the study. Based on an analysis of literary sources, to establish the reasons for the ineffectiveness of screening for tumor diseases of the reproductive organs.

Results. A bibliographic analysis of modern principles and methods of screening showed that the main reasons for unsatisfactory indicators of screening and early diagnosis of OCRO should be considered low screening coverage rates, inconsistency of the legislative framework, inconsistency of the start and end times of the examination and the screening interval, the lack of a unified information base with the ability to record and archive results examinations, a violation of the logistics of exchanging data from studies, a pronounced dissonance of diagnostic capabilities in different regions, the lack of an integrated approach and a unified screening program throughout the country.

Conclusions. One of the possible solutions to the existing problem may be to perform a comprehensive diagnostic examination with a simultaneous assessment of the condition of all organs of the reproductive system, including the mammary glands, with the aim of timely detection of acute cancer with the formation of risk groups for tumor pathology and correction of management tactics.

Key words: screening, breast cancer, cervical cancer, tumor diseases of the reproductive organs.

The increase in the level of cancer incidence, registered throughout the world over the past 10 years, the increase in the number of tumor diseases of the reproductive organs (TDO) in women of childbearing age, insufficient effectiveness of therapy, low rates of detection of tumors in the early stages necessitate the introduction of large-scale screening programs that can provide timely diagnosis of the disease, ideally at the precancer stage, and reduction in mortality rates. The effectiveness of treatment for malignant neoplasms (MNT) is determined by a number of factors, the leading of which is the stage at which the tumor process is diagnosed. It has been proven that timely identification and correction of risk factors can prevent the progression of carcinogenesis, reduce mortality rates and increase the effectiveness of treatment [1–3].

Scientific research in recent decades has established the main trends in cancer incidence, convincingly proving the role of HPV infection in the genesis of cervical, vaginal and vulvar cancer, the influence of genetic determinants on the occurrence of breast cancer, and the relationship between diseases of civilization and tumor progression [4–7].

However, despite active study of the problem, to date the situation with the timely detection of cancer remains unsatisfactory. In Russia, the detection rates of acute cancer in the pre-invasive and early stages are 28.6%, and the majority of patients present with a comprehensive clinical picture, resulting in high rates of one-year mortality, especially for cervical cancer [8, 9]. POROs not only affect the quality and life expectancy of the patient, but also, due to the fact that in 20–40% of cases they are diagnosed in women of fertile age, they adversely affect reproductive function [10–13].

Purpose of the study. Based on an analysis of literary sources, to establish the reasons for the ineffectiveness of screening for tumor diseases of the reproductive organs.

Results and discussion. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, which successfully developed and implemented a preventive medicine program, the tumor prevention system was lost. The result is the current situation, where 26.3% of tumors, incl. visually determined, is diagnosed at stages 3–4, resulting in high cost and low effectiveness of therapy [9, 14, 15]. All researchers note the unacceptably low coverage of the population in Russia by screening programs [1, 8, 16]. Foreign studies conducted over the course of the 20th–21st centuries have convincingly proven that the fundamental principle of effective screening is population coverage of at least 80–90% [17–20]. In our country, opportunistic screening among patients who seek medical help still remains the basis for

identifying acute respiratory infections. And although over the past few years it has been possible to increase screening coverage throughout the country to 40%, in some regions this active detection rate does not reach 20% [14, 19]. Thus, we can say that there is no screening as such.

The introduction of large-scale screening programs in certain regions of our country made it possible to change the current situation for individual nosologies [12, 14, 20, 21]. The epidemiology of cervical cancer in individual regions of the Russian Federation has been sufficiently fully studied, however, in general, over the past 10 years the situation in Russia has not improved [1, 8, 9]. According to the definition of the World Health Organization (WHO), “screening, which is the first stage of clinical examination, involves the examination of practically healthy people who do not have any complaints, and is aimed at identifying asymptomatic cancer or pre-existing conditions.” It has been noted that even ineffective screening can increase detection and survival, but at the same time lead to overdiagnosis [19, 22, 23]. Such “sifting” makes it possible to diagnose underlying diseases and correctable risk factors, such as obesity, metabolic syndrome, prolapse of the vaginal walls, and chronic inflammatory processes [24–27]. Early diagnosis is aimed at people with existing symptoms and signs characteristic of cancer. These patients are also included in screening programs, but not because this is the target audience, but because they come for examination already having the disease. In this population, mandatory screening studies must be supplemented with diagnostic procedures, the scope of which has not yet been developed.

It has been proven that screening measures are effective for two visual forms of cancer: cervical cancer (CC) and breast cancer (BC). Most researchers believe that effective cancer diagnosis requires a combination of only two components: mass coverage of the population and high-tech screening methods with a reliable evidence base of effectiveness [19, 28]. As an example of successful cancer prevention, we can consider the experience of Canada, the USA, Scotland and the Scandinavian countries, where the introduction of clearly regulated screening programs made it possible to reduce mortality rates from cervical cancer and breast cancer [2, 16, 27, 28].

Please understand that it is impossible to prevent all cases of cancer. No screening test has perfect sensitivity, i.e. After each examination, a residual risk remains. The most rapidly progressing cases of cervical cancer, particularly those that occur in adolescent girls and women aged 20 to 24 years, cannot be prevented by currently available screening strategies. With breast cancer, some

tumors are detected during the interscreening period or in the first two years after the last round of screening - the so-called interval cancer cases. The proportion of interval cases varies widely (5–30%); It has been noted that the higher the screening efficiency, the lower the proportion of interval tumors [2, 19, 28]. These tumors are more often found in women with high breast density, with a history of hormone replacement therapy, are characterized by higher aggressiveness and mitotic potential, and have a more unfavorable course and prognosis than screening tumors [20, 26, 29, 30]. During the 20th–21st centuries. In Europe, 17 trend studies were conducted, 12 of them assessed the impact of population-based screening on reducing mortality from breast cancer. Based on the results of these programs, the best European estimate of the reduction in mortality from breast cancer is 25–31% for women invited to screening, and 38–48% for those who actually participate in screening [2, 28]. In women with breast cancer detected as a result of screening, smaller tumors are diagnosed, there are less metastases in the lymph nodes, a lower degree of differentiation and a positive hormonal status are noted [2, 19]. Screening breast cancers have more favorable clinicopathological characteristics and higher survival rates compared to symptomatic tumors [8, 24]. In Denmark, an analysis of screening results proved a convincing reduction in mortality, most pronounced in women under 40 years of age; in the UK, more than 60% of breast cancer screened were cancer in situ and stage I invasive cancer, which led to a significant increase in survival [2, 19, 28].

Ideally, screening tests should effectively identify women with precancerous lesions at high risk of progressing to invasive cancer, providing the opportunity to prevent carcinogenesis with timely treatment; and the intervals between screenings using different methods must be calculated so that invasive cancer does not develop before the next screening. According to some authors, the criterion confirming the accuracy of cervical screening is the detection of Cervical Intraepithelial Neoplasia (CIN) 3, since the vast majority of women with this pathology who were not treated were subsequently diagnosed with invasive cervical cancer [10, 31]. According to the recommendations of the American Society of Colposcopy and Cervical Pathology, detection of CIN2 should not be the main goal of screening, but indicates the need for initiation of treatment. Through organized cervical screening in the USA and European countries, it has become possible to reduce the overall mortality rate from cervical cancer by increasing the detection of cancer at pre-invasive and early

stages, reducing the number of invasive cancers and increasing the survival rate [3, 27, 32].

Important issues in organizing screening are determining the screening age for women included in the early diagnosis program, as well as calculating the screening interval and forming risk groups for the occurrence of PORO. The exact age of women at which breast cancer screening programs are advisable has not yet been determined. In most countries (Norway, Canada, Denmark, Germany, etc.), the screening age for women is 50–69 years. However, there are countries with both a younger age for starting screening programs (Republic of Korea - from 40 years old; Spain and Hungary - from 45 years old) and with a later age at the end of screening (Great Britain - 73 years old, France - 74 years old, the Netherlands - 75 years old) years) [19, 28, 34]. In the USA, the National Institute of Health (The

The National Institutes of Health and The American Association for Cancer Research recommend starting screening mammography at age 50, while the National Cancer Institute (NCI) and the American College of Radiologists (ACR) advocate initiation of a screening program in women over 40 years of age [28]. The NBSS-1 randomized trial (Canada), which examined the effectiveness of screening in the age group 40–49 years versus a group of women over 50 years of age, showed low screening quality rates in young women associated with high breast tissue density and low mammography performance [28, 34–36]. In the USA, Canada, Great Britain, the Netherlands and Sweden, screening mammography is currently performed from 47 to 73 years of age every 2 years, and in risk groups (carriers of a BRCA mutation or cases of familial cancer) - starting from 40 years of age and using MRI of the mammary glands. According to recommendations based on an analysis of the results of the American Cancer Society Guideline Study (ACR, 2015), women at average risk of developing breast cancer should undergo regular screening mammography starting at age 45: between the ages of 45 and 54 years, screening should be performed annually, those aged 55 years and older should switch to biennial screening or have the option to continue screening annually. However, the same document stipulates that women should be able to begin annual screening between the ages of 40 and 44 years. Screening is recommended throughout 10 years or more, the end time is not specified [19, 20, 28].

There is currently no state mammography screening program covering the entire country in Russia. The age at which mammography screening begins in our country remains controversial. Some authors believe that the lower

incidence in women under 40 years of age, additional radiation exposure as a result of the examination, the high frequency of unnecessary invasive interventions in case of overdiagnosis and false negative results reaching 20% due to the higher density of the mammary gland parenchyma in young women outweigh the obtained results. benefit [15, 16, 19, 22]. Other researchers motivate the earlier start of screening by the increase in morbidity among patients under 40 years of age and the predominance of more aggressive histological forms in the structure of tumors in young patients [2, 24, 36]. The situation with determining the age at which screening mammography begins and ends and determining the screening interval is complicated by the inconsistency of orders related to breast examination [37]. In our country, the use of mammography is regulated from 35–36 years old with an examination frequency of 35–50 years, once every 2 years, over 50 years old - once a year for an obstetrician-gynecologist working on the basis of Order No. 572n; for primary care doctors (general practitioners, oncologists) - from 39 to 48 years old, once every 3 years, from 48 to 50 years old, the frequency is not specified, from 50 to 70 years old - once every 2 years, further - not specified (Order No. 869n) or from 39 years old 1 time every 2 years without specifying the completion time (Order No. 1011n). In accordance with the clinical recommendations of the Russian Society of Oncomammologists (ROOM), the recommended (and desirable) age for starting mammographic screening for breast cancer is 39 years or more, the interval is 2 years, regardless of age. In case of clinically detected pathology in the mammary gland, mammography can be performed at an earlier date; its indications and frequency are determined collectively, together with oncologists. In the presence of a genetic predisposition (mutations in the BRCA1 and BRCA2 genes) and family history, it is recommended to start screening at the age of 25 or 10 years earlier than the age at which breast cancer was detected in first-degree relatives. In addition to mammography, MRI and ultrasound examinations of the mammary glands are recommended [28]. The greatest increase in diagnostic efficiency in patients over 35 years of age with a combination of mammography and ultrasound scanning was noted in the case of dense mammary glands [2, 19, 38]. But Order No. 572n does not include ultrasound of the mammary glands in the list of manipulations during the preventive examination of women.

The problem of attracting the population to medical examinations is currently the most acute, since repeated examinations of a limited contingent of the population are not able to affect mortality rates from cancer throughout the

country. Moreover, some “specialists” are disseminating unsubstantiated information about an increased risk of breast tumors during repeated mammography examinations. In Norway, a study was conducted to evaluate new cases of breast cancer associated with radiation exposure as a result of MG screening, which convincingly proved that the risk of regular mammography screening is minimal, and the proven benefits certainly prevail [39]. In recent years, the negative consequences of mass cervical screening, incl. with the inclusion of HPV testing in the examination scheme [40–42]. Potentially harmful consequences associated with detection of precancerous lesions (CIN) include anxiety caused by receiving a positive result after undergoing screening; psychological pressure associated with the detection of a sexually transmitted disease; discomfort from additional diagnostic and therapeutic procedures; high probability of complications [18, 21]. At the same time, the European Society of Medical Oncology considers excisional biopsy a safe method of research, and according to the recommendations of the American Society for Colposcopy and Cervical Pathology (ASCCP) of 2011.

even in pregnant women with suspected cervical cancer, excision is indicated [27, 32].

An unresolved problem is the lack of a uniform standard of screening methods. The method of palpation of the mammary glands does not meet the requirements for screening methods, since the tumor size that can be determined by palpation exceeds 1 cm [7, 24, 28]. Proponents of self-examination and palpation examination of the mammary glands motivate the screening feasibility of these methods by the possibility of early and even self-diagnosis of tumor diseases, however, it should be understood that the minimum tumor size that a woman can detect during self-examination usually exceeds 1.5–2.0 cm. Considering the laws of tumor progression and the volume of tumor cells in a formation of this size, most likely diagnosis will occur at the stage of advanced cancer (stages III–IV) [2, 24]. Based on this, the American Cancer Society no longer recommends clinical breast examination as a screening tool [22].

Mammography is recognized throughout the world as the most effective method for diagnosing early forms of breast cancer [2, 15, 19, 28]. This method allows you to detect formations up to 0.1 cm in size, timely decide on the implementation of additional research techniques, which increases the percentage of detection of malignant tumors at the in situ stage, increases the effectiveness of treatment and preserves the quality of life of treated patients.

The diagnostic value of mammography depends on the type of breast structure and the age of the patient [24, 36, 38].

Mammographic density (MD) characterizes the tissue structure of the breast during X-ray imaging: the ratio of epithelial, stromal (fibrous) and fatty components. Meta-analyses of epidemiological studies demonstrate that an increase in MHD, regardless of other risk factors, significantly increases the risk of breast cancer [7, 23, 30, 36]. High MHL makes it difficult to diagnose especially early stages of breast cancer, therefore, since 2013, in the BIRADS scale, numerical percentage designations have been replaced by letters (types A, B, C, D) [34]. In the United States, legislation has introduced a requirement for mandatory indication of IHL in every report on X-ray mammography. However, in Russia, MHL, unfortunately, is still little used both in assessing the individual risk of breast cancer and for monitoring patients at risk [24].

In young women, ultrasound examination of the mammary glands should be considered the method of choice for high-tech screening [19, 28], since this method makes it possible to detect formations smaller than 0.5 cm and carry out differential diagnosis of various focal formations. Ultrasound examination makes it possible not only to detect a formation in the mammary gland, but also to determine its orientation in relation to the skin surface, as well as to evaluate echogenicity, which is important for the differential diagnosis of benign and malignant pathologies [2, 15, 16]. Some authors recommend ultrasound as an additional screening method in women with high breast density, over 40 years of age, especially with small size and high breast density [20, 38]. However, a randomized study by the American College of Radiology Imaging Network (ACRIN) showed that the combination of MMG and ultrasound, while increasing diagnostic sensitivity, increases the rate of false-positive results, leading to unnecessary biopsies. A method that helps reduce the number of unnecessary biopsies is compression elastography [2, 20], which allows for differential diagnosis of benign and malignant changes and visualization of formations not visible in B-mode. The method is possible as a screening method for high density mammary glands, examination of the mammary gland during pregnancy and lactation, for assessing the condition of the mammary gland in the presence of implants, as a diagnostic method in the interscreening interval. According to the recommendations of the American College of Radiology (ACR) and the American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO), in high-risk patients, the standard of examination is a combination of MMG and ultrasound, especially with high breast density [2, 16, 19].

In our country, these methods, unfortunately, are separated by supervision: MMG is carried out in community clinics, and ultrasound is under the jurisdiction of antenatal clinic doctors, which makes it difficult to collect information together for a real assessment of the clinical situation. The standard of training and advanced training for obstetrician-gynecologists does not include issues of X-ray diagnosis of breast diseases, which leads to non-compliance with diagnostic standards and late diagnosis. Preventive examinations at private medical institutions that are not equipped with appropriate equipment often lead to the substitution of screening methods with other methods. An example would be bioimpedance testing or radiothermometry of the mammary glands instead of X-ray digital mammography.

An isolated examination of the mammary glands does not provide complete information about prognostic risks. The mammary gland forms and functions as a component of the woman's reproductive system, is under hormonal control, and depends on the woman's reproductive behavior and the presence of concomitant gynecological and somatic diseases [7, 24, 26]. To date, more than 80 risk factors for breast cancer have been identified, most of which correlate with gynecological pathology [7, 24, 28, 43]. Awareness of this fact served as the basis for the transfer of mammary glands to the area of responsibility of obstetricians and gynecologists. However, the most valuable diagnostic method remained under the control of general practitioners, therapists and radiologists. The lack of a unified legislative framework regulating screening, the inconsistency of time intervals and the list of diagnostic measures, the division of areas of responsibility according to various nosological forms lead to inconsistency in the actions of specialists, and the lack of a unified information base with the ability to record and archive examination results and non-compliance with the logistics of data exchange between health care facilities violate principles of dynamic clinical observation and lead to diagnostic errors [24, 37]. The vast territory of the country, different economic and demographic situations in the regions determine a pronounced dissonance of diagnostic capabilities in different regions of Russia, differences in the availability of diagnostic techniques for patients in large cities and rural areas. Many regions still use mammography machines that record the results of the study on X-ray film. The loss of the issued conclusion often turns out to be irreparable, preventing dynamic observation. Foreign authors emphasize such a stress factor as the need for a long wait for mammography results. European standards set a period of 10 days for obtaining mammography results and 5 days for further

examination [28]. In Russia, not a single regulatory document provides for mandatory feedback between the antenatal clinic and the mammography room and does not stipulate the timing of the issuance of the report.

After excluding malignant neoplasms, women with benign diseases of the mammary glands are under dispensary supervision of an obstetrician-gynecologist, however, management tactics, methods, frequency and timing of dispensary observation are not defined by Order No. 572n.

Standards for verifying the diagnosis when a malignant process is suspected include mandatory histological examination; if a nodular formation is detected in the mammary gland, clinical recommendations also regulate the performance of a biopsy. The timing of the biopsy, the place where it is performed, the volume and method of collecting biopsy material in our country still remain controversial [24]. Manipulation belongs to the functional responsibilities of the radiologist-mammologist, and the determination of further tactics is the responsibility of the mammologist-oncologist. In the structure of antenatal clinics, there are no such specialists on staff, and women are often simply afraid to go to an oncology clinic, preferring long-term observation.

The basis of cervical screening in most countries is cytological examination [12, 40, 44]. For the first time, cytological screening for cervical cancer began to be carried out in the Canadian province of British Columbia in 1949; in the 50s – in the USA and China, from the beginning

60s – in Japan, Finland, Sweden and

Iceland, since the early 70s. – in Germany, Brazil and other countries. Large-scale cytological screening in the USSR made it possible to reduce the incidence over 25 years (from 1965 to 1989) by 53.1%; in Iceland and Finland, over 20 years, reduce mortality from cervical cancer by 80 and 50%, respectively, in British Columbia - by 75%, in China, the frequency of cervical cancer from 1958 to 1977 decreased by more than 10 times and in the 90s. was only 3.3 per 100,000 women [1, 14, 18].

In our country, traditional cytology with staining according to the Romanovsky or Leishman method is most widely used [11, 27, 31]. A number of researchers note the subjectivity of traditional cytological research, which is a fundamental disadvantage of the method, and low sensitivity for precancerous diseases [21, 32]. A measure to overcome it is considered to be the widespread introduction of liquid-based cytology into practice [12, 18], the advantages of which are the standardization of the obtained material, increasing the adequacy of the obtained preparations, minimizing the human factor, and the possibility of

obtaining repeated preparations for performing HPV tests from an existing sample [27, 32]. However, it should be noted that according to experts from the American College of Obstetrician and Gynecology (ACOG, 2016) and the American Society for Colposcopy and Cervical Pathology (ASCCP, 2012), the sensitivity and specificity of traditional and liquid-based cytology are approximately the same. Most researchers note that the accuracy of diagnosis is determined primarily by the qualifications of the specialists who collect and interpret the material [12, 18, 27, 45]. In determining CIN2+, both methods are recommended for use as part of cervical screening [32].

The most vulnerable aspect of cytological screening is the lack of prognostic capabilities - the obtained material provides information about the state of the cervical epithelium only at the time of the study, and active forms of cancer can develop in the intervals between examinations [6, 10, 46]. A promising direction is screening testing for human papillomaviruses of high carcinogenic risk (HPV HCR). In 10–30% of women who have a normal cytological picture of the cervical epithelium and are carriers of high-oncogenic risk HPV DNA, progression of CIN1 to CIN3 and carcinoma in situ is observed, and 1.5% develop invasive cervical cancer [10]. In the USA, since 2000, HPV testing as a co-test has been recommended for patients with ASCUS; since 2012, after the ATHENA study, HPV testing has been introduced for all women over 30 years of age together with a Pap test; Since 2014, the HPV test (cobas HPV test) has been approved by the FDA for primary screening as an independent method from age 25 [29, 47]. In 2014, a number of countries: the Netherlands, Mexico, Rwanda, Turkey, Italy, British Columbia and Ontario in Canada, Argentina - introduced HPV testing as primary screening; in the UK, HPV HPV typing is used as a co-test; Research is ongoing on the implementation of HPV testing in Australia, New Zealand, Finland, Norway, and Sweden [17, 21, 27]. Positive results from the introduction of HPV testing were obtained in India, Malaysia and Turkey [42, 44, 47]. Compared with women with negative cytology screening results, women with negative HPV testing results have a lower risk of developing CIN3+ and cancer over the next 5–15 years [5, 48]. HPV testing has higher sensitivity but lower specificity compared to cytological studies [21, 45].

In Russia, testing for HPV HCR is included in clinical recommendations for the management of patients with cervical diseases, but is not included in any of the orders regarding screening. Colposcopy helps increase the information content of cervical screening [10, 27, 32]. According to the FIGO recommendations

(2009), colposcopy is recommended for women aged 25–49 years every 3–5 years with a normal colposcopic picture; not recommended after 50 years; up to 25 years of age is recommended in the case of early coitarche, a large number of sexual partners, pathological screening results or a history of CIN, and HIV infection. The use of colposcopy as an independent screening method is not recommended due to difficult reproducibility of results, moderate sensitivity and subjectivity [18, 27, 31]. However, many researchers note that the information content of cytological smears obtained under colposcopy control increases [10, 11, 13], and the number of diagnostic errors when collecting material from the cervix without colposcopic control can reach 25% [10, 49]. According to WHO recommendations

(2014) and ASCO (2017) colposcopy is performed on all HPV-positive patients. In Russia, according to Order No. 572n of 2012, colposcopy is performed when examining women with gynecological diseases; the need and frequency of colposcopy in healthy women during examination is not regulated. Orders No. 839n, 302n and 1011n do not stipulate colposcopy.

Foreign and domestic authors note that joint HPV and cytological testing has reduced the incidence of cervical cancer in the UK over the past 10 years; leads to more frequent detection of CIN3, a reduction in the diagnosis of CIN3+ and cancer during subsequent stages of screening [12, 18, 21, 42, 47], and increases the effectiveness of screening by reducing the incidence of advanced forms of cancer [1, 6, 27].

The screening interval for cervical cancer is currently controversial. The global experience of screening programs demonstrates the abandonment of annual examination, as it leads to a slight increase in the incidence of cancer prevention and an increase in the number of unnecessary interventions [18, 21, 32]. For women aged 21 to 29 years, cytological screening every 3 years is recommended. Women aged 30 to 65 years should be screened with combined cytology and HPV testing every 5 years (preferred) and cytology alone every 3 years (acceptable), ensuring an appropriate balance of benefits and harms of screening.

Russian clinical guidelines of 2017 suggest adhering to the following screening principles: starting screening at the age of 21 or no later than 3 years from the start of sexual activity; further, in the age group of 21–29 years, it is recommended to conduct a cytological examination at least every 3 years; in women 30–69 years old, cytological examination is supplemented with an HPV test, and the examination is repeated at least every 5 years; screening is

stopped if CIN2 or more severe lesions are absent within 20 years [50]. This strategy does not comply with the provisions of Order No. 572n, according to which a smear for oncocytology should be taken annually starting from the age of 18, and HPV testing is not provided as a screening method and is not included in the compulsory medical insurance program. Therefore, at present, the doctor can only recommend that the patient undergo a combined examination, explaining that this meets modern recommendations.

Verification of the diagnosis of CIN and cervical cancer based on the colposcopic picture and cytological conclusion is not justified [10, 27, 50]. The final stage of diagnosis is histological examination of the affected tissue. The choice of method and volume of biopsy is based on the severity of the lesion, the type of transformation zone and the age of the patient [27, 32, 50]. There are frequent cases of underestimation of the degree of epithelial damage based on the material of limited biopsies, there are frequent cases of discrepancies in the results of cytological and histological studies, discrepancies in morphological diagnoses, and artifacts arising from the incorrect use of low-voltage devices make it impossible to adequately assess the pathological process [10].

According to Clinical Guidelines (2017), excision or point biopsy is performed, followed by curettage of the mucous membrane of the cervical canal to exclude the presence of affected tissue in the area above the external os [50]. In the Order of Medical Care for Oncology and the National Guidelines for Gynecology, curettage after excision or conization is considered appropriate. However, Order of the Russian Ministry of Health No. 572n does not require curettage after a biopsy. Such disagreements can lead to fines from insurance companies for performing “unnecessary” interventions and make it difficult to verify the diagnosis.

For CIN3/CIS, standard interventions are Large Loop Electrosurgical Excision of the Transformation Zone (LLETZ), Loop Electrosurgical Excision Procedure – LEEP) or conization, differing in the depth of excision, but the final criteria for choosing between them, as well as the procedure for choosing a biopsy method, have not been determined for CIN2 [10, 27].

Questions regarding the diagnosis and treatment of diseases associated with human papillomavirus infection remain controversial. According to most researchers, CIN are stages of cervical carcinogenesis, and at each stage persistence, progression and regression are possible [12, 16, 25]. With CIN1, the probability of regression is high (60–70%), and CIN2–3/CIS, which regress extremely rarely, is already an obligate precancer. When HPV persists for more

than two years (especially in the case of HPV types 16 and/or 18), there is a high risk of developing CIN3 or CIN3+ in subsequent years [32], therefore, adequate timely treatment of CIN is a secondary prevention of CC [10, 27, 50].

Errors in the differential diagnosis of epithelial lesions of the cervix (LSIL and HSIL) are due to the lack of a unified scope of examination: from minimization - only a virological study [3, 40, 46] - to the inclusion of markers of proliferation and apoptosis, OCT, immunohistochemical and immunocytochemical studies (ICC) in screening), fluorescent diagnostics [18, 21, 50, 51].

The rate of progression of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia to carcinoma is difficult to predict, since according to various sources it ranges from 17 to 70%, and the time required for the development of the tumor process varies [27, 32]. In CIN1, the absolute risk of progression within 2–4 years reaches 15–25% [11, 27]. In recent years, the influence of changes in the vaginal microbiota, systemic and local immune status on the activity of the human papillomavirus has been actively studied [5, 10, 25, 27, 52]; Studies have been conducted to analyze the identification of biomarkers E7, p16ink4D and Ki67 in CIN and cervical cancer [18, 21, 53]. However, despite the high interest in the problem, the factors determining the transition of asymptomatic virus carriage to true neoplasia have not been fully determined [10, 31, 32]. Legislatively, the procedure for forming risk groups for CIN progression and the algorithm for choosing management tactics have not been fully developed. CIN2 can be a manifestation of both LSIL and HSIL, therefore, to clarify, immunohistochemical study (IHC) assessing the expression of the p16 oncoprotein is recommended [10, 27, 31]. However, according to Order No. 572n, IHC is not included in the list of recommended examinations. And the question of choosing a treatment strategy for CIN2 remains unresolved. The effectiveness and feasibility of using immunomodulators with a putative antiviral effect in patients with CIN1 and in the combined treatment of CIN2–3/CIS also remains a subject of debate to date. A number of researchers believe that destruction of the pathological focus is sufficient [54], noting the lack of antiviral drugs; others motivate the need to stimulate antiviral immunity with a high frequency of relapses after surgical treatment [10, 27, 31]. According to L.I. Korolenkova (2016), the medical history of patients with invasive cancer often reveals evidence of inadequate treatment and observation of CIN, as well as obvious errors in determining the degree of neoplasia [10].

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